

Wu Jianxiong cobalt-60 nucleus β decay proves errors in parity non-conservation experiments

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Abstract: In January 1957, Wu Jianxiong used two experimental devices to observe the cobalt 60 decay, and she turned the cobalt 60 nuclear spin in one device to the left with a strong magnetic field at extreme low temperature (0.01 K) and the cobalt 60 nucleus in the other device to the right. She considered the cobalt 60 in the two devices to mirror each other based on the opposite spin direction of the cobalt 60 nucleus in the two experimental devices. There is actually a very significant mistake in this, which is the understanding of mirror symmetry and rotational symmetry, and the cognition of the spin principle of the cobalt 60 nucleus. The cobalt 60 nuclei with the opposite spin direction in the two experimental devices are not the mirror symmetry, but the rotational symmetry of the 180° .

Key words: physical experiments; cobalt-60 nucleus β decay; decay; non-conserved parity; parity conservation; particle spin; ternary equilibrium law; mirror symmetry; rotational symmetry

0 Introduction

What is mirror symmetry? What is the rotational symmetry? Wu Jianxiong in the decay of cobalt 60 test, due to the misunderstanding of these two symmetries, finally created an erroneous experimental conclusion of "parity nonconserved". This paper does not discuss whether the "parity nonconservation" theory itself is correct, but only whether the "parity nonconservation" can be verified by observing two cobalt 60 decays in opposite spin directions.

1 What is symmetry

1.1 What is mirror symmetry and rotational symmetry

The picture above shows the mirror symmetry and rotation symmetry of the cobalt atoms. You can clearly see that after the cobalt atoms have rotated 180° , it is actually the same as the mirror symmetry, but different from the "2 mirror" and "3 mirror". However, in the "Cobalt 60 nucleus β decay parity nonconserved experiment", "2 mirror" and "4 mirror mirror" are confused together. Such error, there are two main points, the first point is the concept of mirror symmetry and rotational symmetry understanding confusion, the second is people through the object rotation inertia thinking to understand the spin of the particles, finally combined with the two concepts of symmetry, finally of the "parity not conservation" experimental conclusion.

1.2 Confusion of the concept of rotation in the trial conclusions

In this trial, there was actually a serious conceptual error. This error is to think that the rotation of the two particles with opposite spin directions in the test is equivalent to the "clockwise" or "counterclockwise" rotation direction change of the human body (object). Finally, this "clockwise" or "counterclockwise" change in the rotation direction is confused with the " 180° rotation of the cobalt 60 atoms". The final experimental conclusion is that the wrong "clockwise" or "counterclockwise" change in the direction of rotation of the cobalt 60 atom is equal to the wrong concept of " 180° rotation of the cobalt 60 atom".

We use the mirror of the "changed rotation direction" of the human body (object) and the mirror of the "180° rotation" to compare the state of the "two cobalt 60 atoms with opposite spin direction" in this trial, while the real state of the "two cobalt 60 atoms with opposite spin direction" is actually the "180° rotation" state. But the tester confused two completely different states: "changed direction of rotation" and "180° rotation".

That is, the true relationship of the two cobalt 60 atoms with opposite spin directions throughout the experiment should be the relationship of "1" and "5" in Fig, but is mistaken for the relationship of "1" and "2". While the true relationship of the two cobalt 60 atoms with opposite spin direction should be the same as that between "1" and "5", but is considered the relationship of "1" and "3" in mirror symmetry.

Due to the confusion of the concept of "symmetry", the experimenter mistakenly considered "3" and "5" due to the same "3" and "2" in the changing direction of rotation of the human body (object). The experimenter confused the notion of "changing direction of rotation" and "180° rotation", so the incorrect perception of "3" and "5" should be the same. Since the results of the experiment found that "3" and "5" were not the same, the "parity nonconserved" experiment was concluded.

That is, the two cobalt 60 atoms with the opposite spin direction are not the relationship between "1" and "2" in Fig, let alone the relationship of mirror symmetry, the same as "2" and mirror "3" in Fig. The two cobalt 60 atoms, with the opposite spin direction, are actually this relationship between "1" and "5" in Fig, and the states that mirror "3" and "5" are not the same.

This experiment actually verified that after two opposite magnetic fields were applied to the two cobalt 60 atoms, the two cobalt 60 atoms are in the 180 rotation state, and the spin direction of the two cobalt 60 atoms is actually the opposite. Instead of simply becoming a state in the opposite spin direction, and making the wrong conclusion that "parity is not conserved".

2 The particle spin and rotation symmetry

2.1 Particle spin

Regarding the basic principle of particle spin production, there are detailed theoretical derivation in the latest version of the Law of ternary equilibrium. Because the derivation process is more cumbersome, so it is not to repeat here, here is only through the existing physical knowledge, to explain why the two cobalt atoms must be mutual 180° rotating state.

We know that when a magnetic field is applied to an object (e. g., a magnet), and some state of the object is changed, it is necessarily the result of the relevant force (e. g., electromagnetic force) produced by this magnetic field. In the existing physical theory, magnets can produce magnetic fields because the magnet internal electrons make a regular circular motion around the nucleus.

Therefore, we can imagine that the interior of the cobalt nucleus may be a certain regular movement of several electrons in a certain space (see new theoretical works of physics for detailed theory, the principle explanation for the charge of objects

in the Law of ternary Balance), and the final irregular spin. So applying a magnetic field to the cobalt nucleus gives its spin in the direction of rotation. When the direction of the magnetic field changes, the cobalt atoms undergo 180° rotation (flip).

This is like applying an additional magnetic field to a magnetic field, and the magnetic pole of the magnet will always maintain the "The polar polar suck and repel polar repel" rule. If the direction of the magnetic field changes, then this magnet must undergo 180 rotation (flip).

2.2 Conclusion

Instead of the β decay experiment of cobalt 60, Wu Jianxiong proves "parity nonconservation under weak interactions", but proves that cobalt 60 is "parity conservation" in nucleus β decay.

3 Conclusion

The principled ambiguity of particle spin formation, and the confusion of the concepts of mirror symmetry and rotational symmetry, are the fundamental causes of the erroneous analysis of experimental results leading to erroneous experimental conclusions.

Ref: [1] 《三元平衡定律》: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4539809>

The English version is converted by translation software, so there may be many translation errors.